

NAME: Kristine A. Hildebrandt
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LG/LID: 691 Lhasa Tibetan
SOURCE(S): Denwood 1999 Tibetan
SAVE AS RTF (RICH TEXT)

Revised Word Questionnaire (Oct 2003)

Depending on the structure of the language, you may need to consult the questions in a reversed order (e.g. look at stress patterns before looking at phonological rules of assimilation, etc.)

For assistance with terms you can consult Bickel's Programm und Verzeichnis der verfügbaren Materialien (on the server)

Or, refer to the .pdf version of the Bickel & Nichols chapter on inflectional morphology (<http://www.uni-leipzig.de/%7ebickel/research/papers/index.html>)

PHONETIC & PHONOLOGICAL QUESTIONS

- You should note forms that the author overtly *describes* (and also covertly *treats*) as phonologically independent. I am especially interested in the *crucial* differences between what is possible (or highly common) within a phonologically independent unit and what is possible at the *edges* or across boundaries
- As you investigate, make an inventory-style comparison of patterns/processes that apply to independent forms with both lexical content and grammatical content. Note what is possible within the form's internal boundaries versus what is possible at the edges (especially if the form is polysyllabic). For example, note possible and required consonant onsets at the initial edge of an independent unit, and compare these to the same onset patterns within the unit.
- If an author says something like "no final consonants" or "no consonants in final position", always check to see if this constraint holds up at syllable edges *within* a phonologically independent form, and at the *ending* edge of the form itself.
- Note also that a form may be phonologically "free" or independent, while not necessarily constituting a lexical category (i.e. "noun" or "verb" or "adjective"). I am especially interested in grammatical forms that are phonologically independent (and also lexical forms that are phonologically dependent upon something else — cannot occur alone phonologically, but they express a meaning that you might otherwise think of as "word")
- Always take from the grammar at least 1 useful example of each thing.
- Look for contradictory or conflicting phenomena (e.g. stress pattern A applies in almost all cases except...). This may be important. In some larger phonological units, one criterion may apply, but the other may suggest a different organization of units.

1. Segmental & Phonotactic Patterns (edges vs. internal)

- occurrence of segments, limitations, prohibitions
- voicing, aspiration patterns
- manner patterns (plosive, affricate, fricative, tap, approx, etc.)
- place (either specific like bilabial, lamino-dental, or general like anterior, coronal, etc.)
- gemination
- vowel height/backness (quality)
- nasal vowels (see "rules")
- vowel length
- VV sequences (includes diphthongs)
- idiosyncratic, segment-specific restrictions or possibilities, like "no labiodental approximants at starting edge, even though they occur medially etc."

The glottal stop ʔ may occur w(, but not in onset, word-medial position.

voiceless aspirated obstruents permitted in word-initial position, but they are always unaspirated when onsets word-medially

l, r only occur pw(

g > ɣ (fricative) when in word-medial onset position, but this does not happen at the starting edge

There are no word-initial consonant clusters (tʃ, tʒ, tr and kj are analyzed as double articulations), but there are possible onset clusters in word-medial position.

Some consonant-combos are resyllabified to C.C word-medially. They include the following combos: gp, gʃ, ɲʃ, ɲtʃ, and ntʃ

Others are syllabified as .CC in word-medial. They include the following: btʒ, mʒ, rg, gtʒ, and nd

Another note of possible interest: s is only found)s when it is the residue of an eroded suffix (past tense, quotative, adverbial "particle"). Otherwise, no s)w

2. "Rules" Part 1

Some phonological processes are restricted in application to the internal domain of a phonologically independent unit, and others are restricted to the boundaries/edges. Sometimes these differences are explicitly noted, others may be implicit. Please list the major processes that highlight such boundaries. Do these things happen to lexical forms only, to grammatical forms only, or to both?

Note types and locations of:

- vowel/consonant HARMONY/assimilation/dissimilation (note the types—place, manner, voicing, other)
- segment DELETION/epenthesis, any kind of insertion/deletion processes
- segment METATHESIS or any type of re-ordering

Only one process/rule seems to be sensitive to pword boundaries: a kind of vowel harmony

In a monosyllabic word, or when a syllable is next to another constituent that in the same word (so, across morph boundaries, but within pword boundary), the vowels in both of the syllables/forms share the same quality of degree of open-ness. This sharing of quality features does not occur across word boundaries.

There are noun particles that are an exception to this. They don't really appear to be pwords because they don't have inherent tone, and they can never be the first initial in a disyllabic pword (so they are always stress-less), but they also don't share the vowel quality features.

So we see:

tɕ^há:-gɪ (and not tɕ^hΛ:-gɪ) 'of the hand'

and rì-nɛ: (and not rì-ne:) 'from the mountain'

The particles that behave this way include:

ablative, plural, genitive

present/future tense

progressive aspect

With verb + multi particle combinations, vowel harmony patterns are more complicated, but the domain is still the pword.

This harmony process applies to adjective + particle combinations too

This might be a 2nd process (although I did not see it explicitly referred to):

C voicing assimilation seems quite common for onset C's word-medially, but in initial position there are both + and - voice C.

e.g. compounds, which are 1 pword,

gǰù 'run' + kǰí 'dog' = (gǰù.gǰí) 'running dog'

It appears that otherwise -asp C's (obstruents) are voiced medially

This is also true for particles, which are not their own pwords, but many of which have an underlyingly unvoiced initial obstruent. This obs is often +voice when they are suffixed to a stem:

k^hóŋ 'he' + kǰí 'gen' = k^hóŋgǰí 'his'

3. "Rules" Part 2

Some rules referring to possible (and prohibited) syllable structures, processes of syllabification, and also to suprasegmental processes are sensitive to the domain of a phonologically independent unit. The distribution of these processes may help to define the boundaries and internal composition of such units.

Note:

--THE DEFAULT syllable template, and whether or not this template applies to the edges of phonologically free units. For example, a language may allow C clusters in coda position, but this may only happen at the ending edge of a phon. free unit, and not internally (or the other way around)

Default syllable template is C1C2V(:)C3, where C1 is onset 1 C2 is the second onset, and C3 is coda

If the syllable = a phonological word, then the V will also have either a high or a low tone. If the syllable is part of a word, then it depends upon which part it is in. If the syllable is the root and is initial, it has an inherent tone that spreads across the word. If the syllable is initial but is a bound "particle" form (that Denwood terms), then it does not have its own inherent tone but picks it up from the next root element (which is generally immediately following). Only a couple of these bound particle forms may possibly be the initial element/syllable in a word anyway.

In addition, if the syllable = a word or is word initial, it will not have a C2. See above phonotactic information for more on this.

C1 can be p, t, ts, k (all asp or unasp), ʔ, tʰ, b, d, dz, tʰ. g, tr, tr, dr, kj, kj gj, m, ɲ, ŋ, ʃ, h, h̃, l, l̃, r, r̃, j

V= a, i ʊ, ε, ɔ with variants depending upon open or (type of) closed syllable

There are 3 other vowels that only occur in the 2nd syllable of disyllabic words: ə, ɪ, o

C2 only occurs word-medially, and those consonants are listed above.

C3 = p or m, or the residue of old C's that are no gone may condition a long vowel.

The older consonants may show up in slow, careful speech, and they are: k, ʀ (old loans), ŋ, and maybe d, l, s, n; the only consonants found at end of word are p, m

There is a historical process involving V:, but this is not a synchronic rule of any kind.

V: does not delineate any word boundaries now.

It does however point to phonological asymmetries between noun + bound morphology and verb + bound morphology. Specifically, the verb appears to be somewhat more phonologically separate from the linkers and the auxiliaries. This is shown by a historical g > V: process that is only reflected nowadays in the verb + linker/auxiliaries, and not in NP. Also, the auxiliaries don't have the same vowel harmony process, and maybe not even tone processes (default high pitch) that NP elements do. This may be an indication that some of the rules (below) that identify pword boundaries are more applicable to NP's than to the verbal complex.

r= alveolar fricative

--C COMBOS— are the same types permitted both internally and at edges?

--syllabification patterns (across syllables internally, vs. across morphemes, vs. across independent units)

No--C combos are only (optionally) permitted in word-medial onset position. And even then, some potential onset cluster types are preferably re-syllabified and broken up into a C.C So some onset cluster ok wd-medial, others still not. but never word-initial or final.

*--SUPER heavy syllables (Hall 2001). Can something that is phonologically free end with a super-heavy syllable? Or can such syllables only be in an internal position? What are the types (e.g. CV:C; CVVC: CVCC)? Can all types occur *anywhere* in a phon. free unit? Note even any seemingly idiosyncratic restrictions (like, might a certain suffix never co-occur with a SHS?, etc.)*

No Super-heavy syllables attested

--STRESS It might be a good idea to look at stress rules first, as these can often clearly illuminate boundaries of phonologically free units—especially if the language only allows "1 main stress per word" or something of that nature. You can then work "backwards" and look at other cues to independent status.

--is there a primary stress rule? what is the domain?

--what types of forms are included, what is exempted?

--what are the minimal/maximal domains for stress to apply? Can a phonologically free unit that is simply (C)V take the main stress?

--can only lexical forms take a main stress, or can independent grammatical forms also take it?

There is a general "high prominence" stress on the initial syllable of a word. In monosyllabic words or on the initial syllables of disyllabic words, this prominence co-occurs with certain vowel quality realizations (a, ε, ɔ). On the non-initial syllables, there is an alternate vowel quality realization that corresponds with non-stress (ə, ɪ, o/ʊ). This appears to be a pattern that holds within the boundaries of a pword.

Denwood says that certain auxiliary particles (which do not appear to be pwords) only have 1 vowel quality type--that of the non-stress vowels.

--TONE Again, another good starting place if other cues are hard to find. Is the domain of tone a syllable? morpheme? phonologically free unit? If the language has syllabic tone, there may still be a word-level domain at work, like "only 1 high per phon. free unit" or something else like this. If grammatical forms take tone, do they also have other features that might suggest that they can stand alone phonologically (like the other stuff listed above)?

Denwood describes tone patterns as one piece of evidence for pword-hood. A monosyllabic word will have either a low or a high tone. On a polysyllabic pword, the initial syllable always carries the contrastive tone pitch, with the 2nd (and 3rd?) syllables always carrying a high pitch.

This is true for multi-morphemic pwords, like compounds and stem + affix combos. This analysis appears to be different from Hari (1977), who describes tone as a morpheme-level phenomenon. She says that some grammatical morphemes carry their own tones, even when combined with root/stem morphemes. She also suggests that each element in a compound carries its own tone assignment, which would make compounds 2 separate pwords then.

--"PITCH ACCENT" In some languages, the apparent tonal contrasts are not clearly defined until they occur on a "larger" unit. Describe the morphological and/or syllabic complexities of such units

4. Minimality & Maximality

Look at the grammar, look also at the dictionary/glossary entries if they are included. What is the most common (or only) minimal and maximal size of a phon. free unit? Or alternatively, what is the minimal/maximal morphological complexity/composition of

something that is phonologically free? (C)V? CV (with an initial crucially present)? di- or polysyllable? How big can a free unit be in terms of syllable number? Do these size constraints apply only to lexical forms? If there are constraints, must a lexical form be bimorphemic to be free? If so, what morphemes qualify? Any & all?

A phonological word may be minimally monosyllabic CV

e.g. kú 'body'

He says that they are not larger than seven syllables in length.

This is 1 pword (according to him--1 tone, 1 stress initial, v-harmony, v-assim)

(j̥):-ky-mɑ-rɪ-bɛ:)pw

be-LINK-NEG-AUX-INTERR

'Isn't it likely to be there?'

this is also 1 gword, because of co-occurrence and ordering restrictions.

5. Reduplication

Is the entire unit copied? More? Less? Can something of any phonological size/complexity have reduplication (even if the process is semantically restricted)? If there are different *types* of reduplication, see if you can find patterns, or note what the author says.

Is the resulting suprasegmental pattern of a reduplicated form the same or different from a single free form? (Are there 2 main stresses or 1? 2 tones? a different tone altogether?)

1 special type of nominalizing (derivational) reduplication, whereby adjectives reduplicate and become nouns. The result, Denwood says, is a single phonological unit.

1 tone, 1 phonation option on the word-initial C, vowel harmony across the reduplicated word. The question is: what is copied? He gives no pre-reduplicated form, and I cannot locate these adjectives (in unreduplicated form) in any other part of the grammar.

Example:

tɕ^húŋ.dzu: 'small (thing?)'

This looks like a templatic strategy in either case--a CVC syllable type (heavy preferred)

This resulting single pword reduplicated form is different from "phrasal adjectives", which Denwood argues are 2 pwords because each element carries its own tone, its own vowel harmony, its own phonation alterations, etc.

e.g.

khám tàŋ.bʊ 'clean'

state clear.NOM

This is 2 pwords, but 1 gword comprised of 3 morphemes (co-occurrence restrictions, ordering restrictions)

Another kind of reduplication that looks like resulting form is 2 pwords:

"Rhyming Redup"--but I don't know what the pre-redup base might be.

there is a vowel alternation like a-ɪ or a-ɔ across words

2 pwords--2 tones, and the initial C of the 2nd element may be aspirated

e.g.

kári kóri 'dilly-dallying'

làŋɪ líŋɪ 'dangling' (this is a good ex. because 2nd element carries low tone, which would

not happen if they were 1 pword)

6. Other Questions

Note any discussion & descriptions of phonological boundaries attributed to interruption or pause phenomena. Also note if the author argues for boundaries because of repair phenomena. Examples. Only in the more detailed grammars will you probably see such discussions.

7. Phonological Units in Morphologically Complex Forms

--COMPOUNDING: note any patterns of segmental alteration with compounds—especially at the edges of compounds; note prior and resulting stress/tone patterns; note segmental restrictions in compounds (e.g. in Manange, the 2nd element may never have an aspirated onset, even if the onset of the form when it is free is aspirated).

Again, note any conflicts of properties (e.g. in Lhasa Tibetan, a compound has 2 tone contours, but there is vowel harmony that spreads across the entire compound, and only a single main stress)

Sometimes in a compound, a piece of one of the elements may be deleted. If this happens, note any patterns, because this may suggest that one of the elements is in fact not a single phonological unit.

A bit of a problem with analyzing compounds because Denwood does not give transcriptions of each element outside of compound. However, I have found a couple of examples that suggest the resulting compound is 1 pword (see the "running dog" example above)

He calls these compound-things "disyllabic nouns with etymologies as 2 free-standing units" possible combos: N + N, N + Adj, Adj + N and a couple of others.

1 word: 1 tone, vowel harmony, voicing assim, 1 stress initial

e.g.

m̃:dʒu: butter + cheese 'dairy products'

tý:dõ: trunk + short 'shirt'

There is only 1 example of a compound from 3 former words:

p̃éndzø:gã: 'library'

book.store.building

Not sure what pre-compounded forms are like, but 1 pword (1 tone, vowel harmony, v assim)

--"SIMPLE juxtaposition or concatenation of 2+ independent forms"—these are things that might be called "serialization" in some grammars: note any phonological discussion of these things. single tone? single stress? segment changes? ordering restrictions? co-occurrence restrictions?

"Serial Verbs" in LT:

They look like separate pwords, but behave as parts of a single clause, with 1 verb-form providing directional, valency adjusting or aspectual information, and the 2nd verb form being the movement/state verb. Thus, they appear to be parts of a single gword--no noun may intervene, always refer to the same subject/participant in the clause (unless valency adjustment-causation), and the only particle that may intervene is an optional "serial

particle". In addition, they generally have a conventionalized meaning. Denwood: "vary in terms of grammaticization and phonological independence" Sometimes both elements have a productive life outside of the serial combination, sometimes not.

e.g.

(k^hɔ̌)pw (gjàgɑ:-lə)pw [(trø: (tʃɛ:))pw (jɔ̌ŋ-bə-re:)pw]gw

3.sg India-loc flee (SER) come-LINK-AUX

'he came fleeing here to India'

It looks like the serial linker is not its own pword (no tone), and probably is best analyzed as a suffix to the preceding word. However, it appears to retain its voiceless initial C, which would probably become voiced through voicing assimilation if it were really phonologically bound.

The serial linker is generally optional, but in some cases Denwood says it is necessary when different subject needs to be overtly indicated.

Other 2-word phrases:

Proper names and place names are often 2 separate words combined into a single pword-compound:

e.g.

ɲɛnsõ: 'hell' (obviously, a place....)

evil.gone

ʃíɡədzɪ 'Shigatase' (place in Tibet)

estate.peak

Phrasal Nouns are 2 pwords--They often refer to religious items

e.g.

tɕ^híŋə táɡdzɪ 'Chingwa Takstse' (a religous-location castle)

--MULTI-morphemic forms: this is already discussed in above sections, but note especially phonologically free units that are minimally bimorphemic (or bigger), note any allomorphy that suggests that multi-morphemic forms behave as a single phonological unit.

--IF a language has a wide variety of inflectional affixes, do all stem-affix combinations have the same/similar stress, syllabification, segmental patterns, phon rules, tones, etc? Describe those that deviate from the set "general" patterns. Give examples. In German, for example, a stem + certain suffixes behaves as a **single** phonological unit ([li:.bx] 'love 1.sg'), but a stem + certain other suffixes behaves as **2** phonological units ([li:p.liç] 'dearly')—the resyllabification & voicing of the plosive is evidence of this.

Be sensitive to exceptions/variations in segmental/phonotactic, prosodic rules that may suggest that certain things "go together" phonologically, and others that do not. Explicitly state the conditions under which variations apply.

Here are some grammatical morphemes that appear to behave as their own pwords (e.g. they have independent tone, they have their own domain of vowel harmony and C voicing assim or

phonation changes):

1. *tā*: 'coordinating particle' (but no tone), but treated by Denwood as phonologically independent. Why? Not discussed.
2. each element of a phrasal verb (different structure than serial verbs) are pwords: two tones, 2 vowel harmonies, 2 phonation differences. However they appear to be 1 gword because part 1 always directly precedes the stem, which is inflected with whatever suffixes are necessary.

e.g.

káɛ: *gǰǰp* 'work hard'

slow *strike*

3. Post-positional nominal elements/words

they include numeratives, specific markers, comparative forms

Are probably not their own gwords

But they can carry independent tone, may be both mono or disyllabic, have internal vowel harmony

Denwood says they occupy a "deictic" position in the NP

e.g.

k^há 'square'

k^hàga: 'different'

They can be the head of a phrase (so a syntactic word?), but particles cannot stack up on them like they can with lexical noun or verb roots/stems

e.g.

(rɛː)pw *(k^há)pw* *(ɕɛ̀ndaː)pw* *(ts^háɪmə)pw* *(p^hánd-zo)pw*

cotton *square* *other* *all* *yonder-NOM*

'all those other squares of cotton (over yonder)'

4. relative and interrogative pronouns are their own pwords--individual tones (e.g. *sà*: 'what')

5. other pwords: numerals, time words (adjectives), quantifiers

6. verbs of being, what we might think of as evidentials, because they carry information like *be/be.at* + evidentiality/epistemic info. They carry their own tones.

The word "particle" comes up frequently in Denwood's grammar. Most of these particles are best analyzed as not being pwords, and not gwords either, so they are probably suffixes.

Here are particles that are not pwords:

(cannot be monosyllabic words or occur alone in a phrase (unlike N or V), and cannot occur as the initial syllable of a polysyllabic word.; they often occur as "part of a word", where the word = a noun or verb; they often follow the word, but some precede; some of them may coalesce with the final vowel of the root/stem. They also do not take tone, but see the 3 exceptions below))

The one evidence for their own gword status comes from the fact that the meaning of the combination of stem + particle is always predictable by the meaning of the individual parts, even though the particle itself has only a "grammatical meaning".

Auxiliaries (with verbs) *náɪ* 'give + *sũ* AUX = *(náɪsũ)pwd* 'gives/is giving'

modals

case markers

topic marker (*ni* and *da*)

dual and plural markers (e.g. ɪʔà-ɪʔi: 'Pro.2= we/us 2')

nominalizers

A couple of "particles" that may in fact be pwords. They tend to "pre-fix" or prepose the verb stem, and thus can be the location of the contrastive tone. One question is if these elements are still not tone-bearing and the tone of the following root spreads both left-ward and rightward. I don't have any information on this though.

tā: 'and/with'

tʔi: 'a/an'

ma 'not'

Denwood says that ma appears to carry a low tone, but there is some question as to its phonological status.

Another questionable particle is the "polariser/polar" particle. It often means NEG or dubitative. It appears to not be a pword, but it has some location options in its affixing. It can be prefixed to the verb root, or it can occur between the linking particle and the auxiliary (within a multimorphemic gword).

MORPHOLOGY & SYNTAX QUESTIONS

The goal here is to identify individual grammatical forms (or combinations of forms) as independent units (grammatical units/grammatical words). In some cases, these forms (or combinations of) exist as syntactic units, at other times as morphological units. Still other times, the distinctions will be collapsed or blurred. The primary interest here is not whether or not they are phonologically independent, although it is important to note whether or not the things you're describing are free or bound. This is because we will be creating a 3rd dedicated database that charts the overlaps/alignments between things that are phonologically free and things that are morpho-syntactically free.

8. Create a (glossed) list of inflectional morphemes (the types) described. Note the distribution of each morpheme:

--with what MUST they co-occur (bound or free)?

--with what else MAY they (optionally) co-occur (bound or free)?

--if they co-occur with multiple different types of forms (either as a host or attached to a host), are the resulting meanings always the same, or are they different? Note the differences with examples.

--can other elements ever be inserted between morpheme forms that comprise a stem + infl. form unit? See if adverbs can do this.

See discussions above

9. Note the overall constituent ordering patterns in the language. Is the pattern rigid, somewhat fluid, very fluid? Do all inflectional/grammatical elements that are called "free" follow the same ordering possibilities as lexical elements? Do they consistently appear in a single ordering scheme or co-occurrence scheme despite being phonologically independent.

Pay special attention to so-called particles, or other minimally free forms.

Word order is generally SV/AOV, but the nominal order is somewhat fluid. The ordering of particles with respect to roots/stems is fixed, with individual exceptions noted above.

10. Does the author discuss grammatical forms/combinations with a conventionalized meaning or coherence? In other words, are there grammatical combinations with 1 meaning, and that meaning is lost or irretrievable (or totally different) when a piece of the form is missing or when the form is analyzed piece-by-piece? "Constructions" might be a way that grammarians describe this.

See discussions above with respect to phrasal verbs, phrasal adjectives, particles

11. Are there elements with some degree of ordering or grammatical freedom, but that seem to be phonologically bound? Describe their distribution. Are there elements that appear to be phonologically independent (see above criterion), but have a fixed order or co-occurrence constraint? Describe these too. Pay special attention to things the author calls clitics.

Nothing called a clitic--everything is referred to as "particles"

12. Is a grammatical unit always bigger than a single morpheme? Always the same size? Are there some grammatical units that are a single morpheme, but others that are combinations? What is the biggest possible grammatical unit in the language (in terms of numbers of morphemes), and what is the smallest? Pay attention to, for example, the NP, and then also the elements that make up the NP. Then, note the predicate, and then the things that make up the predicate (may be called the "verbal complex").

13. Looking at the main verbal complex in the grammar, how morphologically complex is it? Looking at the predicate of the clause, how many verbs or verb-like elements must be present? verb-only? verb + aux form? 2 + verbs? If aux forms appear, is there a minimal amount (like, there must be at least 1 aux), or is there a maximal amount (like, there can be no more than 3...). In English, for example, in the predicate, there can be just 1 verb (=gword), but there can maximally be up to 1 verb plus 3 or so other gword forms (auxiliaries plus the main verb). (degree of synthesis)

A single predicative gword can have a root-stem plus 4 or more grammatical morphemes:

jyː-ky-ma-n-bɛ:

be-link-NEG-AUX-NEG.POL

'Isn't it likely to be there?'

This is also 1 pword

Some interesting observations regarding pword and verbs. There are 2 types of verbs, "simple", monosyllabic verb stems, and these things called phrasal verbs.

It appears that phrasal verbs are 2 separate pwords because they may each carry independent tones. However, they operate together as 1 gword because of co-occurrence restrictions and another piece of evidence is that the first element of a phrasal verb often carries an abstract or unclear meaning, and it can only be understood when it is thought of in terms of the phrasal pair. Here is an example:

[(há)pw (mà-kɔ-wɛ:)pw]gw

*understand?? NEG-understand/hear-NOM.OF
'of not understanding'*

An additional piece of evidence for pword (general) he cites: pauses--a pause may occur before and/or after a pword, but not within (I guess no matter what the size).